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Yoga as Panacea for Psychological Distress among Students in Times of Covid-19.

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On Managing Academic Life of Students in the Time of Pandemic

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Abstract

What is Psychological distress ? If we try to explain in simple words it is the baggage of thoughts-often unnecessary , the burden of pain , the feelings of hurt, trauma,anger,fears or phobias, worries of all sorts, uncertainties, depression, stress , repeated thoughts,ego, emotional turmoil , failures, expectation, desires etc. This effects our life, productivity, creativity,growth, development and subsequently results in psychological, physical or psychiatric ailments etc. Stress is often at the heart of many ailments like cardiovascular diseases, lifestyle diseases,hormonal problems, Irritable bowel syndrome other gastro-intestennial problems etc , In Yogic terms this are explained as vrittis or wanderings of the mind and Maharishi Patanjali defines Yoga as Yoga Chittavrittihi Nirodaha. The Yoga Vasistha defines Yoga as Mana Prasamana Upaya Yoga ityabhi dhiyate, which means one that silences the mind is Yoga. The thoughts are like constant storms raging in our mind and Yoga teaches us to have efficient control over them. It is said the mind is a bad master but a good servant. Maharishi Patanjali has given us the concept of Astanga Yoga or eight fold path of Yoga which has powerful effect on the mind-body mechanism and overcoming psychological distress and inducing psychological well-being and it is backed by evidence based research.Research has shown that psychological distress among students, especially in this Covid era is growing. Research studies also points to the powerful impact of Meditation, Pranayama, Mindfulness , integrated approach of Yoga therapy on psychological distress of various types. Yoga is also about non-violence, love, peace, harmony which can remove distress not only from the individuals mind but also from collective human consciousness,distress from the world at large etc. Yoga has the ability to bring Global peace and order .

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Yoga as Panacea for Psychological Distress among Students in Times of Covid-19.

What is Psychological distress ? If we try to explain in simple words it is the baggage of thoughts-often unnecessary , the burden of pain , the feelings of hurt, trauma,anger,fears or phobias, worries of all sorts, uncertainties, depression, stress , repeated thoughts,ego, emotional turmoil , failures, expectation, desires etc. Psychological distress has two important components anxiety and depression. Psychological distress affects our life, productivity, creativity,growth, development and subsequently results in psychological, physical or psychiatric ailments etc. Covid-19 has led to lockdown of educational institutions, classes affecting students across the globe. These has severely affected higher education especially technical education which is not possible fully through online means . It can raise career concerns among students. A variety of other factors too can affect students in this era of pandemic.Research conducted among students in mainland China has shown that anxiety and depression levels among students in Covid times is higher than in normal times.

The causes of Psychological distress can be financial or economic, disease, worry, fear, sudden setbacks or unpleasant events, loss of a loved ones, career worries, worries of jobs loss, remaining in lock downs which results in social disengagement, worries about family members , parents or elders in family, loss of family members, lack of social support, lack of communications, addictions including tech addictions, poor time management , lack of exercise, obesity, company , inefficient time management , engagement in unproductive activity, negativity or tendencies to blame oneself etc

Psychological distress can exhibit itself in several ways like anxiety, stress, frustration, addictions/drugs , lethargy, sleep, inactivity, anger, reactivity, violence, inefficient time

management, depression, sleeplessness, over thinking, disharmony at home or office , tech addictions , engagement in non-productive engagement, lack of focus, concentration , fear or phobias, worries , lack of mindfulness etc.

Prolonged isolation can cause psychological distress during covid-19. Shorter sleep period was found to be associated with depression in a study conducted in China. The fear of getting infected and spreading the diseases among the family members was another reason for Psychological distress. The study also found that graduating final year students had more depression and PTSD symptoms than students in the other years. The study also suggest suitable measures counselling ,training measures in high risk population or colleges or universities with higher rates of psychological distress (Tang et al., 2020).

Methodology

At the very outset an attempt has been made to understand psychological distress

Next we have tried to understand Yoga

Third we have tried to study the research studies on psychological distress and possible findings.

The study deals with existing studies on Yoga and psychological studies

We have also made an attempt to study the impact of Covid-19 on psychological distress in students.

The methodology used is of secondary data to arrive at conclusions.

Hence, literature review forms important component of our study and hence this study can also be said to be a review study.

Psychological Distress and Prevention

Mirosky and Ross (2013) suggests three ways to tackle Psychological distress 1) Education in well being or training 2) Good job or income source or business which provides option for creativity, balances work and family 3) Supportive relationship.

Again , drugs may not be fully the solution as they suppress the problem but do not address the root causes.

Yoga and Psychological Distress

The word Yoga has come from the root word Yug - that is which joins. But what is that Yoga joins - it brings about the integration of mind, body, soul; the harmonious development of individual; the individual consciousness to cosmic consciousness. It is in other words the realization of the latent divinity within us and the divinity in everyone. Maharishi Patanjali has given the world the unique concept of Astanga Yoga which can be said to be panacea for psychological distress. The astanga yoga or eight fold path of Yoga consists of Yama, Niyama, Asana, Pranayama, Pratyahara , Dharana, Dhyana, Samadhi. The Yama, Niyama are considered the foundation of Yoga. There are five Yamas- Satya (Truth), Ahimsa (Non-violence), Brahmacharya (Celibacy), Asteya (Non-stealing), Aparigraha (Non-possession) and five Niyamas (Saucha Cleanliness), Santosha (Satisfaction), Swadhaya (Self-study), Iswarpranidhanaya (Surrender to God) . The five Yamas and Niyamas can be said to form the base of Yoga. The Yamas play a powerful role in reducing psychological distress. We can take an example - Non-violence which means non-hurting anyone physically, mentally or with our

words. Brahmacharya which means self control, self restraint. Santosha is self satisfaction which tells us to be satisfied with our present condition and be thankful to almighty. Swadhaya, Ishwarpranidhanaya helps us to cultivate patience, faith and fortitude. These are key behavioral tools and key to psychological well being.

Maharishi Patanjali talks about the 9 obstacles to Yoga and they are disease, dullness, doubt ,carelessness, laziness, overindulgence ,illusions, failure to reach firm ground and slipping from ground gained or regression. These 9 obstacles have clear resemblance as depression in psychology.1. Maharishi Patanjali gives several ways to overcome this obstacles which include single minded effort, regular practise or abhyasa . Maharishi Patanjali in the very first sloka says Yogas Chittavrittih Nirodaha and in the second says Atha Yoga Anusasanam that is Yoga is discipline. Often in psychological distress we can see the vrittis to be very prominent and a in disciplined life. Maharishi Patanjali Yoga Sutra is a unique treatise on not only Yoga, Astanga Yoga but the dynamics of health, mind, consciousness, soul, powers, psychology , liberation from pain and suffering etc. Yoga today is being studied from many angles which include psychology, health, spirituality, philosophy etc. The Bhagwat Gita talks about different types of Yoga which include Karma Yoga, Bhakti Yoga, Gyan Yoga, Dhyana Yoga etc. So Yoga has such a wide perspective .

Yoga and Research Studies on Psychological distress

According to Bhusan (1998) a yogic lifestyle results in a reduction of negative affects, it has therapeutic value for those who carry somatic or psychological problems, and it can be safely used as an instrument of psychological wellbeing.

Telles, et al. (2018) in their study find that 15 days of residential yoga program involving teachers which include physical exercises, Pranayama and guided relaxation led to significant improvement in mental well being and state anxiety.

A meta-analytical study conducted by Lin et al. (2011) has found positive impact of Yoga on psychological health of cancer patients and suggests it as possible adjunctive therapy for cancer patients in managing psychological distress.

As per the findings of a study by bilderbeck et al. (2013) Yoga may be effective in improving subjective well-being, mental health, and executive functioning within prison populations.

Another Meta-analytic study by Cramer, Lauche, Langhorst, & Dobos (2013) involving 12 RCT and 619 participants suggest that yoga could be considered an ancillary treatment option for patients with depressive disorders and individuals with elevated levels of depression.

According to another Meta-analytic study conducted by Mehta & Sharma (2010) found that majority of the study were able to significantly reduce depressive symptoms in patients, however it suggests overcoming certain methodological limitations

In healthy individuals, biomarker studies suggest that yoga influences neurotransmitters, inflammation, oxidative stress, lipids, growth factors, in a manner largely similar to what has been shown for anti-depressants and psychotherapy (Phillips et al., 2003).

Mindfulness based Yoga Practices in women in their third trimester showed greater reductions in perceived stress and trait anxiety (Beddoe et al., 2009).

A study suggest that women who are more distressed are more likely to accept psychological support before starting an IVF cycle and that in these women HathaYoga practice is associated with distress reduction (Valoriani et al., 2014).

The results suggest a significant decrease in psychological morbidity such as anxiety state and trait, depression, treatment-related symptoms and improvement in the quality of life in the yoga group as compared to the controls following surgery in early stage breast cancer undergoing surgery (Rao et al., 2008)

In a study conducted by Shastri, et al. (2017) involving Yoga Pranayama, Vedic Mathematics , Control it was found that Significant changes took place in mindfulness , aggression, emotional regulation in the Yoga group ; significant changes in mindfulness only in the Vedic mathematics group and aggression in the control group.

Again a technique like Sudarshan Kriya Yoga has been found to be beneficial in treatment of stress, anxiety, post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD), depression, stress-related medical illnesses, substance abuse, and inmates and rehabilitation of inmates (Brown & Gerbarg,,2005)

One of the meta analysis study done by on the effects of meditation, Yoga, mindfulness on depression, anxiety in Tertiary education , found moderate effects which decreased substantially when interventions were compared to active control (Bredvelt et al., 2019) .

Discussion and Conclusion

Human Brain can be said to be one of the most important things and determines his/her destiny or life, career, productivity, relationship. Human Brain is not merely structural but has a component of thoughts, behaviour, emotions, ego etc. This component when they grow wrong

can play havoc in human life. Hence it is important especially among students to be psychologically healthy. The nations health depends upon the psychological health of its students. Covid -19 has had its effects on psychological health of students and this is evident from the studies across the globe. But at the same we have mounting evidence that Yoga plays a vital role in management of psychological health in students and others. Yoga plays a vital role in reducing psychological distress especially anxiety, stress, depression, anger management, addictions, increasing I.Q , E.Q , memory , creativity which is quite vital in the life of students etc. And all this is now backed by research. In that context we can say that Yoga should be integrated in our educational life which will help promote values, DE-addiction, crime free society and happy and healthy nation and world. The meta-analytical studies done also point to the beneficial effect of Yoga on Psychological distress and well being but they suggest longitudinal studies or long term studies, removal of bias , neutrality , experimenting with bigger sample, overcoming methodological limitations, specific application, real time or functional studies, correlating with pathological basis etc . However, the evidence that we have clearly says the foundation of integrative medicine so that the benefits of Yoga are made available to all

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